

Available online at: <https://ijact.in>

Date of Submission	26/09/2019
Date of Acceptance	03/11/2019
Date of Publication	30/11/2019
Page numbers	3453-3461(9 Pages)

Cite This Paper: Fouad M Salama, Norhashidah M Ali. Fast $O(N)$ hybrid method for the solution of two dimensional time fractional cable equation, 8(11), COMPUSOFT, An International Journal of Advanced Computer Technology. PP. 3453-3461.

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An International Journal of Advanced Computer Technology

ISSN:2320-0790

FASTO(N)HYBRID METHOD FOR THE SOLUTION OF TWO DIMENSIONAL TIME FRACTIONAL CABLE EQUATION

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Abstract: It is the time and memory consuming when numerically solving time fractional differential equations as it requires $O(N^2)$ computational cost and $O(MN)$ memory complexity. N and M are the total number of time levels and space grid points, respectively. In this paper, we present an efficient hybrid method with $O(N)$ computational cost and $O(M)$ memory complexity in solving the two-dimensional time fractional cable equation. The Laplace transform method and implicit finite difference scheme are used to derive the hybrid method. The stability of the numerical scheme has been carried out. Numerical results show that the hybrid method compares well with the exact solution and performs faster compared to a standard finite difference scheme.

Keywords: Fractional cable equation; Caputo fractional derivative; Laplace transform; Finite difference scheme; Stability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The history of fractional derivative is nearly as long as integer derivative [1, 2]. The fractional differential equations (FDEs) can be defined as differential equations that contain fractional derivatives [3]. Fractional derivative can describe the hereditary and memory properties of real-world phenomena more accurately than integer-order derivative. This interprets the extensive usage of fractional differential equations for modelling many problems in engineering [4, 5], physics [6, 7, 8], bio science [9], hydrology [10], finance [11, 12, 13] and so on.

Particularly, the cable equation plays a fundamental role in describing the electrophysiological behaviors through neuronal processes [14]. The fractional cable equation (FCE) is nearly identical to the classical cable equation, however, the time and/or space derivatives for the FCE are of arbitrary order. Henry et al. [15] has modified the cable equation to generate the fractional cable equation, which has been utilized for describing the anomalous diffusion in spiny neuronal dendrites. As the

fractional derivative can indicate the history of the state in all intervals, the fractional cable equation model is better than the frequent cable equation [15,16].

For the most of FDEs, analytic solutions cannot be obtained explicitly [17], so the considerations of developing numerical methods for solving these equations have increasing importance. Among the existing numerical methods, finite difference methods have been widely used for solving several types of FDEs[18-21]. In regard to 1D fractional cable equations, Liu et al. [22] have suggested two implicit finite difference schemes for solving the time fractional cable equation. They proved the unconditional stability and convergence of one scheme by using the Fourier analysis method. Quintana-Murillo and Yuste [23] considered the time fractional cable equation with two fractional Riemann-Liouville derivatives. They used the Grunwald-Letnikov formula to discretize the fractional derivatives along with the forward difference and three-point centered formulas to approximate the integer derivatives. The Von Neumann method is employed for determining the stability and convergence. Chen et al. [24]

presented a numerical scheme with first order accuracy in time and fourth order accuracy in space for the variable-order nonlinear fractional cable equation. The Fourier analysis technique was used to prove that the method is unconditionally stable and convergent. Hu and Zhang [25] designed two compact finite difference schemes for solving the time fractional cable equation with Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative. The energy method is applied to investigate the stability and convergence of one compact scheme. Later, Karatay and Kale [26] derived a difference scheme, which is based on the Crank-Nicolson finite difference method for solving the fractional cable equation involving Caputo fractional derivative. Unconditional stability and convergence are proved by the spectral stability technique.

For two-dimensional problems, Ghehsareh et al. [27] derived a numerical scheme for the 2D linear time fractional cable equation. At the beginning, they used implicit difference schemes for discretizing the fractional and integer order derivatives. Thereafter, the local radial point interpolation (LRPI) method was extended and utilized for solving the semi-discretized issue. The stability and convergence of their technique have not been discussed. A fourth-order compact finite difference method for solving the 2D fractional cable equation was proposed by Yu and Jiang [28]. The relationship between Riemann-Liouville and the Grunwald-Letnikov fractional derivatives was utilized to discretize the fractional order derivatives. They analyzed the stability and convergence of their method by means of the Fourier method. Balasim and Ali [29] derived two implicit finite difference schemes, which were applied for the solution of the time fractional cable equation which involves temporal Caputo fractional derivative. The stability and convergence of the schemes have not been provided. Li et al. [30] proposed a compact finite difference scheme for the fractional cable equation with fourth-order accuracy in space and second order accuracy in time. The stability and convergence of the numerical scheme are proved by the Fourier analysis method.

The two-dimensional time-fractional cable equation (2D TFCE) studied in this paper is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t) \\
 &= b_x \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + b_y \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \mu_0 u(x, y, t) \\
 &+ f(x, y, t),
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

with the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, y, 0) = g(x, y), \tag{2}$$

$$u(0, y, t) = g_1(y, t), \quad u(L, y, t) = g_2(y, t),$$

$$u(x, 0, t) = g_3(x, t), \quad u(x, L, t) = g_4(x, t), \tag{3}$$

$$0 \leq x, y \leq L, 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

where $0 < \alpha < 1, b_x, b_y$ and μ_0 are positive constants, and the term ${}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t)$ denotes the Caputo time fractional derivative of order α defined by [3]

$${}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{u^{(n)}(x, y, \xi)}{(t - \xi)^{\alpha+1-n}} d\xi,$$

$n - 1 < \alpha < n, n \in \mathbb{N}.$

A major challenging issue of finding numerical solutions for time fractional differential equations is the non-local property of the fractional derivative. This necessitates the solution at all previous time levels to be stored so that a considerable amount of memory space is required. Another difficulty of numerically solving time fractional differential equations using finite difference methods is the large computational cost $O(N^2)$ [31-33]. For more about the computational challenges of fractional differential equations, please refer to [33]. These issues make the implementation of finite difference methods time-memory consuming. To overcome such computational issues, several methods including parallel computing [32, 34], short memory principle [35] and pre-conditioner techniques [36] are suggested. On the contrary, numerical solution of the classical time dependent partial differential equations (PDEs) needs to be stored only at a specific number of time levels and the computational cost is linear with respect to N . In this regard, Ren et al. [37] proposed a method which is based on the Laplace transform and linearization property to approximate the Caputo fractional derivative so that the fractional PDE is converted to a corresponding PDE. They verified the applicability of their method by solving 1D and 2D time fractional diffusion equations. In another study carried out by Bishehniafaret al. [38], they employed Ren's approach to reduce 1D fractional PDE to the corresponding PDE. Afterwards, an approximate analytical solution is obtained by using the separation of variables method for solving the approximating PDE. The aim of this study is to develop an economical computational solution for the 2D TFCE (1). The Laplace transform will be employed to approximate the time fractional derivative and reduce the TFCE (1) to its corresponding PDE. An implicit difference scheme will then be applied to solve the resulting PDE, which reduces the computational cost and memory usage significantly.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we introduce the formulation of the hybrid method for the solution of (1). The unconditional stability of the numerical scheme is proved by the Fourier method in section 3. For the comparison, section 4 gives a brief overview of an existing standard implicit finite difference scheme for solving the TFCE (1). The computational complexities of both the standard and developed hybrid methods are discussed in the same section. Numerical experiments are conducted to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed method in section 5. Finally, conclusion is made in section 6.

II. FORMULATION OF THE HYBRID METHOD

In this section, we describe the derivation of the proposed hybrid method for solving problem (1). Regarding this matter, the approach in [37] is to be used to approximate the Caputo fractional derivative so that the TFCE (1) is converted to a PDE; then, we develop an implicit finite difference scheme to solve the resulting PDE. Firstly, we recall the Laplace transform of the Caputo fractional derivative [3]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{ {}_0^C D_t^\alpha f(t) \} &= \int_0^\infty e^{-st} ({}_0^C D_t^\alpha f(t)) dt \\ &= s^\alpha F(s) \\ &\quad - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} s^{\alpha-k-1} f^{(k)}(0), \\ &\quad n-1 \leq \alpha \leq n, n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

For $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, the Laplace transform is then given by

$$\mathcal{L}\{ {}_0^C D_t^\alpha f(t) \} = s^\alpha F(s) - s^{\alpha-1} f(0),$$

where $\mathcal{L}\{f(t)\} = F(s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} f(t) dt$.

Due to the non-local property of the fractional derivative, solving problem (1) using standard finite difference schemes (such as implicit scheme with a certain discretization formula for the Caputo fractional derivative) requires the storage of the solution values at all previous time steps to compute the solution at the current time step. To overcome this issue, we use the Laplace transform to approximate the Caputo time fractional derivative ${}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{ {}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t) \} &= s^\alpha U(x, y, s) \\ &\quad - s^{\alpha-1} u(x, y, 0), \\ &= s^\alpha [U(x, y, s) \\ &\quad - s^{-1} u(x, y, 0)], \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where $U(x, y, s)$ is the Laplace transform of $u(x, y, t)$.

As we have $0 < \alpha < 1$, the term s^α can be linearized as follows

$$s^\alpha \approx \alpha s^1 + (1 - \alpha) s^0. \tag{5}$$

By substituting (5) into (4), yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{ {}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t) \} &\approx \alpha s [U(x, y, s) \\ &\quad - s^{-1} u(x, y, 0)] \\ &\quad + (1 - \alpha) [U(x, y, s) \\ &\quad - s^{-1} u(x, y, 0)]. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Using the inverse Laplace transform, (6) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} & {}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t) \\ & \approx \alpha \frac{\partial u(x, y, t)}{\partial t} \\ & + (1 - \alpha) [u(x, y, t) \\ & - u(x, y, 0)]. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

By considering (7), the original 2D TFCE (1) is simplified to the following PDE

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} &= B_x \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + B_y \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \eta u(x, y, t) \\ &\quad + (r - 1)g(x, y) \\ &\quad + rf(x, y, t), \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$u(x, y, 0) = g(x, y), \tag{9}$$

$$u(0, y, t) = g_1(y, t), \quad u(L, y, t) = g_2(y, t),$$

$$u(x, 0, t) = g_3(x, t), \quad u(x, L, t) = g_4(x, t), \tag{10}$$

$$0 \leq x, y \leq L, 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

in which $B_x = \frac{b_x}{\alpha}$, $B_y = \frac{b_y}{\alpha}$, $\eta = \frac{1-\alpha+\mu_0}{\alpha}$ and $r = \frac{1}{\alpha}$ are positive constants.

We consider the solution of the PDE (8), which gives an approximate solution for the original problem (1). Let the spatial domain be uniformly discretized in both x and y coordinates, such that $x_i = i\Delta x$, $y_j = j\Delta y$, $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M_x$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M_y$, where $\Delta x = L/M_x$, $\Delta y = L/M_y$ are the space mesh size, and $t_k = k\Delta t$, $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$. $\Delta t = T/N$ is the time increment.

Let $u_{i,j}^k$ be the approximate numerical solution at the point (x_i, y_j, t_k) , the following implicit finite difference equation is obtained by utilizing the forward and centered difference formulas for the time and space partial derivatives, respectively about the point (x_i, y_j, t_{k+1})

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{u_{i,j}^{k+1} - u_{i,j}^k}{\Delta t} \\ &= B_x \left(\frac{u_{i+1,j}^{k+1} - 2u_{i,j}^{k+1} + u_{i-1,j}^{k+1}}{\Delta x^2} \right) \\ &+ B_y \left(\frac{u_{i,j+1}^{k+1} - 2u_{i,j}^{k+1} + u_{i,j-1}^{k+1}}{\Delta y^2} \right) \\ &\quad - \eta u_{i,j}^{k+1} + (r - 1)u_{i,j}^0 + rf_{i,j}^{k+1} \\ &\quad + O(\Delta t + \Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2). \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

By neglecting the higher order terms in (11), the finite difference approximation for the PDE (8)-(10) with the initial and boundary conditions are obtained as follows

$$u_{i,j}^{k+1} = \frac{1}{1 + \eta\Delta t + 2d_1 + 2d_2} [d_1(u_{i+1,j}^{k+1} + u_{i-1,j}^{k+1}) + d_2(u_{i,j+1}^{k+1} + u_{i,j-1}^{k+1}) + u_{i,j}^k + (r - 1)\Delta t u_{i,j}^0 + r\Delta t f_{i,j}^{k+1}], \quad (12)$$

Where, $i = 1, 2, \dots, M_x - 1, j = 1, 2, \dots, M_y - 1$ and $k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$.

$$u_{i,j}^0 = g(x_i, y_j), \quad (13)$$

$$u_{0,j}^k = g_1(y_j, t_k), \quad u_{M_x,j}^k = g_2(y_j, t_k),$$

$$u_{i,0}^k = g_3(x_i, t_k), \quad u_{i,M_y}^k = g_4(x_i, t_k), \quad (14)$$

$$0 \leq x, y \leq L, 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

where $d_1 = B_x \Delta t / \Delta x^2$ and $d_2 = B_y \Delta t / \Delta y^2$.

III. STABILITY ANALYSIS

Throughout this section, the Fourier method is utilized to investigate the stability of the implicit difference scheme (12). Let $U_{i,j}^k$ be the approximate solution of Eq. (12). Then the error is expressed as:

$$\zeta_{i,j}^k = u_{i,j}^k - U_{i,j}^k. \quad (15)$$

Next, $\zeta_{i,j}^k$ satisfies Eq. (12), so the round off error equation can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & -d_1(\zeta_{i+1,j}^{k+1} + \zeta_{i-1,j}^{k+1}) \\ & + (1 + \eta\Delta t + 2d_1 \\ & + 2d_2)\zeta_{i,j}^{k+1} \\ & - d_2(\zeta_{i,j+1}^{k+1} + \zeta_{i,j-1}^{k+1}) \\ & = \zeta_{i,j}^k + (r - 1)\Delta t \zeta_{i,j}^0. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

For $k = 0, 1, \dots, N$, the following grid function is defined

$$\zeta^k(x, y) = \begin{cases} \zeta_{i,j}^k, & x_{i-\frac{\Delta x}{2}} < x < x_{i+\frac{\Delta x}{2}}, y_{j-\frac{\Delta y}{2}} < y < y_{j+\frac{\Delta y}{2}} \\ 0, & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{\Delta x}{2} \text{ or } L - \frac{\Delta x}{2} \leq x \leq L \\ 0, & 0 \leq y \leq \frac{\Delta y}{2} \text{ or } L - \frac{\Delta y}{2} \leq y \leq L \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

in which $\zeta^k(x, y)$ can be expanded in Fourier series as

$$\zeta^k(x, y) = \sum_{q_1, q_2 = -\infty}^{\infty} \lambda^k(q_1, q_2) e^{2i\pi(q_1 x/L + q_2 y/L)}. \quad (18)$$

such that $I = \sqrt{-1}$, and

$$\begin{aligned} & \lambda^k(q_1, q_2) \\ & = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \int_0^L \zeta^k(x, y) e^{-2i\pi(q_1 x/L + q_2 y/L)} dx dy. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

By utilizing the l^2 norm and the Parseval equality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\zeta^k\|_2^2 & = \sum_{i=1}^{M_x-1} \sum_{j=1}^{M_y-1} \Delta x \Delta y |\zeta_{i,j}^k|^2 \\ & = \sum_{q_1, q_2 = -\infty}^{\infty} |\lambda^k(q_1, q_2)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Now, suppose the solution of Eq. (16) has the following form

$$\zeta_{i,j}^k = \lambda^k e^{I\beta i \Delta x} e^{I\gamma j \Delta y}, \quad (21)$$

where $\beta = 2\pi q_1/L$ and $\gamma = 2\pi q_2/L$.

Substituting (21) in Eq. (16) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^{k+1} & = \frac{1}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} \lambda^k \\ & + \frac{(r - 1)\Delta t}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} \lambda^0, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where

$$\rho_1 = 4d_1 \sin^2 \frac{\beta \Delta x}{2}, \quad \rho_2 = 4d_2 \sin^2 \frac{\gamma \Delta y}{2}.$$

Proposition 3.1: The implicit finite difference scheme defined in Eq. (12) is unconditionally stable.

Proof. First, we use the mathematical induction to prove the following result

Suppose λ^{k+1} ($k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$) form the solution of (22), then

$$|\lambda^{k+1}| \leq |\lambda^0|, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1. \quad (23)$$

For $k = 0$, we get

$$\lambda^1 = \frac{1 + (r - 1)\Delta t}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} \lambda^0.$$

Since $r - 1 < \eta, \rho_1, \rho_2 \geq 0$ then

$$|\lambda^1| \leq |\lambda^0|. \quad (24)$$

Now, assume that

$$|\lambda^s| \leq |\lambda^0|, \quad s = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (25)$$

From (22) and (25), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\lambda^{k+1}| &= \left| \frac{1}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} \lambda^k + \frac{(r-1)\Delta t}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} \lambda^0 \right| \\
 &\leq \left| \frac{1}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} \right| |\lambda^k| \\
 &\quad + \left| \frac{(r-1)\Delta t}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} \right| |\lambda^0| \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} |\lambda^0| + \frac{(r-1)\Delta t}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} |\lambda^0| \\
 &= \frac{1 + (r-1)\Delta t}{1 + \eta\Delta t + \rho_1 + \rho_2} |\lambda^0|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $r - 1 < \eta, \rho_1, \rho_2 \geq 0$ we have

$$|\lambda^{k+1}| \leq |\lambda^0|.$$

According to Eq. (20) and (23), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\zeta^{k+1}\|_2^2 &= \sum_{q_1, q_2 = -\infty}^{\infty} |\lambda^{k+1}(q_1, q_2)|^2 \\
 &\leq \sum_{q_1, q_2 = -\infty}^{\infty} |\lambda^0(q_1, q_2)|^2 = \|\zeta^0\|_2^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

So, we get

$$\|\zeta^{k+1}\|_2 \leq \|\zeta^0\|_2, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1,$$

which means that the implicit scheme is unconditionally stable.

IV. REVIEW OF EXISTING STANDARD SCHEME

In this section, we present an existing standard implicit finite difference scheme considered to solve the TFCE (1) for comparison. In order to illustrate the computational efficiency of the hybrid method, computational complexity analysis in terms of total number of arithmetic operations to be implemented and memory space requirement for the hybrid method in comparison with the standard method is also conducted in this section.

In their investigation into finding numerical solution for the problem (1), Balasim and Ali [29] derived an implicit finite difference scheme where the following approximation formula was used to discretize the Caputo fractional derivative [39]

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}_0^C D_t^\alpha u(x_i, y_j, t_{k+1}) &= \frac{\tau^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \sum_{s=0}^k b_s (u_{i,j}^{k-s+1} - u_{i,j}^{k-s}) \\
 &\quad + O(\Delta t^{2-\alpha}),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $b_s = (s + 1)^{1-\alpha} - s^{1-\alpha}$, and the following fully discrete scheme was then given to solve TFCE (1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\tau^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \sum_{s=0}^k b_s (u_{i,j}^{k-s+1} - u_{i,j}^{k-s}) &= b_x \left(\frac{u_{i+1,j}^{k+1} - 2u_{i,j}^{k+1} + u_{i-1,j}^{k+1}}{\Delta x^2} \right) \\
 &\quad + b_y \left(\frac{u_{i,j+1}^{k+1} - 2u_{i,j}^{k+1} + u_{i,j-1}^{k+1}}{\Delta y^2} \right) \\
 &\quad - \mu_0 u_{i,j}^{k+1} + f_{i,j}^{k+1} + O(\Delta t^{2-\alpha} + \Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2).
 \end{aligned}$$

For the sake of simplicity, the above standard scheme can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{i,j}^{k+1} &= \frac{1}{1 + \delta\mu_0 + 2r_1 + 2r_2} \left[r_1 (u_{i+1,j}^{k+1} + u_{i-1,j}^{k+1}) \right. \\
 &\quad + r_2 (u_{i,j+1}^{k+1} + u_{i,j-1}^{k+1}) + u_{i,j}^k \\
 &\quad + \sum_{s=1}^k b_s (u_{i,j}^{k-s} - u_{i,j}^{k-s+1}) \\
 &\quad \left. + \delta f_{i,j}^{k+1} \right], \tag{26}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, M_x - 1, j = 1, 2, \dots, M_y - 1$ and $k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$, and

$$\delta = \Delta t^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha), r_1 = \frac{b_x \delta}{\Delta x^2}, r_2 = \frac{b_y \delta}{\Delta y^2}.$$

From Eq. (26), it is obvious that the solution outcomes at all previous time levels required being stored to compute the solution at the current time level. This indicates that there are $NM_x M_y$ values to be stored in the memory. Without loss of generality, and ignoring the memory usage of the coefficients, initial condition and source term, 8 bytes of memory space are needed to store each value, which means that the standard method (26) requires about $8NM_x M_y$ bytes of memory space. For instance, it requires 100 GB with $M_x = 10240, M_y = 10240$ and $N = 1024$. Contrarily, and from Eq. (12), one can note that the solution needs to be saved only at two time levels, k and $k + 1$ until the desired time level N is reached. This means that there are only $2M_x M_y$ solution values to be saved in the memory. Thus, the hybrid method requires only $16M_x M_y$ bytes of memory space. Based on what have been discussed, the memory requirement of the hybrid method is of $O(M)$ which is far smaller than the standard method of $O(NM)$, where $M = M_x M_y$.

Besides the more memory space required when utilizing the standard scheme, the considerable computational cost which makes the scheme implementation time consuming is the other issue. In order to get u_{ij}^{k+1} , the right-hand side of Eq. (26) must be computed. Assuming the coefficients are evaluated and stored beforehand, each grid point of time level t_{k+1} requires $6 + (k)$ additions and $4 + (k)$ multiplications. There are $(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1)$ grid points at each time level. So, each time level requires $(10 + 2(k))(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1)$ arithmetic operations. As $k = 0 \rightarrow N - 1$, and from (26), the whole computational cost for the standard scheme is

$$\begin{aligned} &10N(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1) \\ &\quad + 2(1 + 2 + \dots + N - 1)(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1) \\ &= 10N(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1) \\ &\quad + 2\left(\frac{N(N - 1)}{2}\right)(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1) \\ &= (N^2 + 9N)(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, the evaluation of each grid point u_{ij}^{k+1} using Eq. (12) requires 6 additions and 7 multiplications where the coefficients are computed and stored beforehand. There are $(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1)$ grid points at each time level. So, each time level requires $13(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1)$ arithmetic operations to be performed. Since there are N time levels, the total computational cost using the hybrid method is about $13N(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1)$. Based on this discussion, the total computational cost of the hybrid method is of $O(N)$ which is much less expensive than the standard method of $O(N^2)$. Table 1 summarizes the memory requirement and computational cost for both standard and hybrid methods.

Table 1: Memory requirement and computational cost for standard and hybrid methods

Method	Memory requirement	Computational cost
Standard	$8NM_xM_y$	$(N^2 + 9N)(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1)$
Hybrid	$16M_xM_y$	$13N(M_x - 1)(M_y - 1)$

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we give some numerical results to test and illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed method in solving the two-dimensional time fractional cable equation (1). In the numerical experiments, both standard scheme (26) and the hybrid method developed in section 2 were applied so that their performance can be analyzed on the same platform. These methods were carried out in Mathematica 11 and run on Windows 10 operated by Intel Quad Core processor with 8 GB of RAM. Using the same spatial step in both x and y directions, various time steps of 24, 36, 48, 60 were considered for different space steps of 12, 18, 24, and 30. The Gauss-Seidel method with a

relaxation factor equal to 1 was utilized to generate the numerical results. Tolerance $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$ and l_∞ norm were used for convergence criteria.

Example 1. The following time-fractional cable equation is considered [29]

$$\begin{aligned} &{}_0^c D_t^\alpha u(x, y, t) \\ &= \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - u \\ &\quad + \left((1 + 2\pi^2)t^2 + \frac{2t^{2-\alpha}}{\Gamma(3 - \alpha)} \right) \sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y), \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

with initial and boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, 0) &= 0 \\ u(0, y, t) &= 0, \quad u(1, y, t) = 0, \\ u(x, 0, t) &= 0, \quad u(x, 1, t) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

and the exact solution is given by

$$u(x, y, t) = t^2 \sin \pi x \sin \pi y.$$

Table 2 – 6 compares the computed values of execution time (in seconds), maximum absolute error (Max) and average absolute error (Ave) by both standard and hybrid methods when $\alpha = 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7$, and 0.9 . Numerical results show that the proposed hybrid method performs 4.28 – 12.57 faster than the standard schemes while the numerical solution still in good agreement with the exact solution. Table 7 highlights the memory space usage of both standard and hybrid methods for different time and space steps. It can be observed that the hybrid method has almost 3.33 – 8.33% less memory usage than the standard method. Figure 1 illustrates the execution time for both standard and hybrid methods when $\alpha = 0.3, 0.5, 0.7$. We can note that the proposed method requires much less computational time than the standard scheme, which is in agreement with the computational complexity analysis in the previous section..

Table 2: Comparison between standard [29] and hybrid methods at $\alpha = 0.1$

$M_x = M_y$	N	Method	Execution time (sec)	Speedup	Ave	Max
12	24	Standard	13		2.4183E-3	5.0728E-3
		Hybrid	3	4.33	2.3726E-3	4.9772E-3
18	36	Standard	114		9.1207E-4	2.0188E-3
		Hybrid	19	6.00	8.4364E-4	1.8676E-3
24	48	Standard	517		3.4008E-4	7.7413E-4
		Hybrid	64	8.07	2.6196E-4	5.9711E-4
30	60	Standard	1672		1.6712E-5	4.6582E-5
		Hybrid	161	10.38	7.8300E-5	1.9250E-4

Table 3: Comparison between standard [29] and hybrid methods at $\alpha = 0.3$

$M_x = M_y$	N	Method	Execution time (sec)	Speedup	Ave	Max
12	24	Standard	12		2.4140E-3	5.0640E-3
		Hybrid	2.8	4.28	2.4909E-3	5.2255E-3
18	36	Standard	107		9.1249E-4	2.0198E-3
		Hybrid	16	6.68	9.0926E-4	2.0132E-3
24	48	Standard	491		3.4230E-4	7.7931E-4
		Hybrid	53	9.26	2.9897E-4	6.8198E-4
30	60	Standard	1526		1.7245E-5	4.7594E-5
		Hybrid	130	11.7	6.1751E-5	1.6278E-4

Table 4: Comparison between standard [29] and hybrid methods at $\alpha = 0.5$

$M_x = M_y$	N	Method	Execution time (sec)	Speedup	Ave	Max
12	24	Standard	11		2.4518E-3	5.1434E-3
		Hybrid	2.2	5.00	2.8059E-3	5.8865E-3
18	36	Standard	96		9.3354E-4	2.0666E-3
		Hybrid	14	6.85	1.1585E-3	2.5651E-3
24	48	Standard	431		3.5732E-4	8.1372E-4
		Hybrid	44	9.79	5.1574E-4	1.1748E-3
30	60	Standard	1346		2.0277E-5	6.0423E-5
		Hybrid	107	12.57	1.3577E-4	3.3041E-4

Table 5: Comparison between standard [29] and hybrid methods at $\alpha = 0.7$

$M_x = M_y$	N	Method	Execution time (sec)	Speedup	Ave	Max
12	24	Standard	9		2.5761E-3	5.4044E-3
		Hybrid	1.9	4.73	3.1633E-3	6.6362E-3
18	36	Standard	77		1.0127E-3	2.2423E-3
		Hybrid	12	6.41	1.4468E-3	3.2034E-3
24	48	Standard	343		4.1088E-4	9.3604E-4
		Hybrid	39	8.79	7.7059E-4	1.7546E-3
30	60	Standard	1101		5.4376E-5	1.4951E-4
		Hybrid	93	11.83	3.6942E-4	8.6341E-4

Table 6: Comparison between standard [29] and hybrid methods at $\alpha = 0.9$

$M_x = M_y$	N	Method	Execution time (sec)	Speedup	Ave	Max
12	24	Standard	8		2.9315E-3	6.1501E-3
		Hybrid	1.7	4.70	3.3400E-3	7.0074E-3
18	36	Standard	62		1.2418E-3	2.7499E-3
		Hybrid	11	5.63	1.5653E-3	3.4659E-3
24	48	Standard	261		5.7913E-4	1.3195E-3
		Hybrid	39	6.69	8.5759E-4	1.9529E-3
30	60	Standard	771		1.8834E-4	4.4965E-4
		Hybrid	88	8.76	4.4021E-4	1.0268E-3

Table 7: Memory requirement of both standard [29] and hybrid methods for different space and time steps

$M_x = M_y$	N	Method	Memory usage (bytes)
12	24	Standard	27648
		Hybrid	2304
18	36	Standard	93312
		Hybrid	5184
24	48	Standard	221184
		Hybrid	9216
30	60	Standard	432000
		Hybrid	14400

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 1 Comparison of execution times when (a) $\alpha = 0.3$ (b) $\alpha = 0.5$ (c) $\alpha = 0.7$.

VI. CONCLUSION

A hybrid method based on the Laplace transform and implicit finite difference scheme for the two-dimensional time-fractional cable equation has been presented in this paper. The hybrid method has the advantage of low computational cost of $O(N)$ and low memory complexity of $O(M)$. The Fourier method has been used to prove the unconditional stability of the numerical scheme. A comparison of a standard finite difference scheme with the hybrid method has shown that the proposed method is feasible, accurate and superior to the standard scheme in terms of computational complexity and CPU computational times.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from Universiti Sains Malaysia Research University Grant (1001/PMATHS/8011016).

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